

AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON THE DETERMINANTS OF SUCCESS IN SMEs

Dr. Manoj Kumar Jha
Professor, IINTM , New Delhi, India

Abstract

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in the economies of both developed and developing countries, representing well over 90 per cent of all manufacturing enterprises in the world. Nevertheless, the folklore is that some of these enterprises collapse within a few years of their start up. Of those operating, some have grown rapidly, while others lagged behind or grew slowly. Therefore, it is important to identify the causes of failure as well as the factors contributing to the success or growth of these enterprises. Furthermore, the causes of failure and factors of success may vary from country to country, depending on their economic, geographical and cultural differences. Therefore, empirical investigation into these aspects of SMEs in different countries is important. The findings of this research will be useful to economic development planners as well as to individual entrepreneurs. This paper attempts to analyse the main factors that are perceived to have contributed to the progress or success of these enterprises. The analysis will be based on the perceptions of owner/managers who responded to a questionnaire survey conducted on a sample of manufacturing enterprises in Delhi, Ghaziabad and Greater Noida. The statistical technique of factor analysis will be use for analysing the data. The results may indicate a set of identifiable factors that have positive and significant impact on the success of the sample firms. These factors will be ranked in their order of importance for the success of SMEs.

Key words: *SMEs, Developed and Developing Countries, Economic Development Planners*

*Corresponding author: * Dr. Manoj Kumar Jha

Reference this paper as: Dr. Manoj Kumar Jha , “An Empirical Study on the Determinants of Success In SMEs ” *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, Vol. 2, Issue 1, Jan-Feb-2014, pp 53-65,*

INTRODUCTION

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in the economies of both developed and developing countries, representing well over 90 per cent of all manufacturing enterprises in the world (Wijewardena and Cooray, 1995). Nevertheless, the folklore is that some of these enterprises collapse within a few years of their start up. Of those operating, some grow rapidly, while others lag behind or grow slowly. Therefore, it is important to identify the causes of failure as well as the factors contributing to the success or growth of these enterprises. Furthermore, the causes of failure and factors of success may vary from country to country, depending on their economic, geographical and cultural differences. Therefore, empirical investigation into these aspects of SMEs in different countries is important because the findings of such research are useful to economic development planners as well as to individual entrepreneurs in the countries concerned.

Questionnaire Survey

For the questionnaire survey, a sample of 350 manufacturing enterprises was drawn from the India Telecom Telephone Directory – (Yellow Pages) . Since the telephone directory did not list the SMEs separately, the sample included manufacturing firms belonging to all three sizes—small, medium and large. The strategy was to identify the SMEs at the time of recording responses to the questionnaire. Moreover, the authors wanted to include large firms also in the survey as some data representing all sizes of firms could be used for another study.

In addition to the general questions on the nature and performance of each firm, 25 factors that would be likely to contribute to the success or growth of manufacturing SMEs in a developing country like India were included in the questionnaire. The complete questionnaire was pre-tested on a small group of manufacturers and finalized before it was utilized for the survey. Three hundred fifty copies of the questionnaire along with a letter of request addressed to the chief executive officer (CEO) of each firm were mailed to the sample firms.. Respondents were asked to indicate their perception on each of these factors according to a five-point Likert scale. The scale for each factor ranged from 1 = Least important to 5 = Most important. A total of 262 firms responded to the questionnaire, giving a response rate of 75 per cent. Since 14 responses were not useable due to incomplete data and 80 responses were from large firms, the total useable

responses representing SMEs amounted to 168. The profile of these 168 firms is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Profile of the sample firms

Type of Industry	Firms	%
Chemical, petroleum, rubber and plastic products	42	25.0
Electronic and electric equipment	10	6.0
Fabricated metal products, machinery and transport equipment	12	7.1
Food, beverages and tobacco products	22	13.1
Furniture, fixtures, lumber and wood	14	8.3
Machinery, computer, and transportation equipment	8	4.7
Paper and paper products	18	10.7
Stone, clay, glass, and concrete products	8	4.8
Textile and wearing apparel	28	16.7
Miscellaneous	6	3.6
All firms	168	100.0

Forms of Organisation	Firms	%	Employees	Firms	%
Sole proprietorship	30	17.9	1 – 100	88	52.4
Partnership	26	15.5	101 – 200	51	30.4
Private limited company	112	66.6	201 – 300	29	17.2
All firms	168	100.0	Total	168	100.0

Results of the Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis of data was carried out in two stages. Firstly, the technique of factor analysis was utilised to reduce the number of variables to a few meaningful factors, each representing separately identifiable characteristics that could be considered as a set of principal components or determinants of success in manufacturing firms. “Factor analysis has the ability to produce descriptive summaries of data matrices, which aid in detecting the presence of meaningful patterns among a set of variables” (Dess and Davis, 1984, p. 472). However, before using the factor analysis, a number of initial tests were conducted to determine the suitability of our data for such an analysis. The correlation matrix produced by SPSS showed a considerable number of correlations exceeding 0.3. The Bartlett test of sphericity was significant ($P = .000$). Furthermore, the anti-image correlation matrix revealed that all of the measures of sampling adequacy were well above the acceptable level of 0.5, confirming the suitability of our data for a factor analysis. Secondly, descriptive statistics were used for ranking the factors in their order of importance.

When the original 25 variables were analyzed by the principle component factor analysis with varimax rotation, a six-factor solution emerged in 26 rotations, with an eigenvalue of ≥ 1 . Then, two variables were dropped from the analysis because of their low loadings and difficulty of interpretation. The analysis of the remaining 23 variables yielded six significant factors, which explained 61.1 per cent of the total variance. These factors were also considered satisfactory according to the reliability test of Cronbach’s alpha with a value greater than 0.6 (Cronbach, (1951). These six factors and the variables loaded against each, along with the relevant statistical values, are given in Table 2. The factor loadings have ranged from 0.787 to 0.450. The higher a factor loading, the more its test reflects or measures a factor. The literature on factor analysis shows that loadings equal to or greater than 0.40 are considered large enough to warrant interpretation (Kerlinger, 1979, p.189.). Thus, only factor loadings greater than 0.4 are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Principal Components Factor Analysis – Varimax rotation

Factors contributing to the success of manufacturing enterprises

Variable	Factor 1 Efficient management	Factor 2 Marketing strategy	Factor 3 Customer orientation	Factor 4 Supportive environment	Factor 5 Capital accessibility	Factor 6 Product quality
Efficient team of management	0.724					
Production efficiency and productivity	0.707					
Strong and exemplary leadership	0.702					
Systematic planning for the future	0.701					
Acquiring high-calibre workforce	0.658					
Good relations with employees	0.533		0.515			
Effective cost management	0.503					
Advertising and promotional activities		0.760				
Use of external advisory services		0.732				
Emphasis on specialised markets		0.612				

New product development		0.567				
Commitment to customer satisfaction			0.785			
Good relations with customers			0.754			
Good service and delivery system			0.471			
Competitive prices of products			0.450			
Open economic policy of the government				0.701		
Political stability & peaceful environment				0.675		
Government assistance/tax incentives				0.572		
Availability of capital					0.784	
Availability of bank loans & other credit					0.773	
Availability of quality raw materials						0.734
Use of new technology and automation		0.535				0.564

Maintaining high quality of products						0.530
Eigenvalue	3.97	2.86	2.64	2.12	1.95	1.67
Proportion of Variance Explained	15.4%	11.4%	10.4%	8.4%	7.5%	6.5%
Cumulative Variance Explained	15.92%	27.3%	38.2%	46.4%	54.3%	61.1%
Alpha	0.85	0.76	0.77	0.72	0.69	0.59

Factor 1: Efficient management. This factor was represented by seven variables with factor loadings ranging from .728 to .507 (Cronbach’s alpha = .85). They were efficient team of management, production efficiency and productivity, strong and exemplary leadership, systematic planning for the future, acquiring high-calibre workforce, good relations with employees, and effective cost management. Although the variable “good relations with employees” was correlated fairly highly with Factor 3 as well, considering its higher loading and importance it was included in Factor 1. This factor accounted for 15.9 per cent of the rated variance.

Factor 2: Marketing strategy. Four variables with loadings ranging from .761 to .569 (Cronbach’s alpha = .76) belonged to this factor and they included advertising and promotional activities, use of external advisory services, emphasis on specialised markets, and new product development. This factor explained 11.5 per cent of the rated variance.

Factor 3: Customer orientation. This factor comprised four variables representing commitment to customer satisfaction, good relations with customers, good service and delivery system, and competitive prices of products. Factor loadings of these variables ranged from .786 to .450 (Cronbach’s alpha = .77). A variance of 10.6 per cent was explained by this factor.

Factor 4: Supportive environment. Three variables were included in this factor. They were open economic policy of the government, political stability and peaceful environment in the country,

and government assistance and tax incentives. Their factor loadings ranged from .703 to .574 (Cronbach’s alpha = .72). The factor explained 8.5 per cent of the variance.

Factor 5: Capital Accessibility. This factor comprised two variables, namely, the availability of capital, bank loans and other credit. They carried factor loadings of .787 and .777 respectively (Cronbach’s alpha = .69). The factor explained 7.8 per cent of the variance.

Factor 6: Product Quality. This last factor consisted of three variables relating to the high quality of products. They were the availability of quality raw materials, use of new technology and automation, and high quality of products. Their factor loadings ranged from .739 to .534. The variance explained by this factor amounted to 6.7 per cent. Although the reliability of this factor with a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of .59 was marginally below the minimum acceptable level of .6, considering the nature and importance of the variables involved, it was included in the analysis. Further, although the variable “use of new technology and automation” was loaded fairly highly on Factor 2 as well, because of its higher loading and greater relevance it was also included in this factor.

Relative importance of factors

Ranking of the above six factors in order of their importance, along with mean and standard deviation, is shown in Table 2. The importance of these factors, as perceived by the respondents, has been ranked on the basis of their mean values. The closer the mean to 5, the higher is the importance of the factor. Accordingly, the ranking followed the following order: (1) customer orientation, (2) quality products, (3) efficient management, (4) supportive environment, (5) capital accessibility, and (6) marketing strategy. Their means ranged from 4.4781 to 3.3814.

Table 3: Ranking of Factors according to their Importance

Factor	No. of variables	Mean	S.D.	Rank
Factor 1: Efficient management	7	4.2777	0.6491	3
Factor 2: Marketing strategy	4	3.3814	0.9547	6

Factor 3: Customer orientation	4	4.4781	0.6487	1
Factor 4: Supportive environment	3	3.5924	1.0578	4
Factor 5: Capital accessibility	2	3.5603	1.0834	5
Factor 6: Product quality	3	4.3264	0.6418	2

Discussion

The results of the factor analysis show a set of six separately identifiable factors that have positive and significant impact on the success of manufacturing enterprises in India. Although efficient management and marketing strategy emerged as the first and second most highly loaded factors respectively, customer orientation has been ranked by our respondents as the most important factor for the success of their enterprises. Similarly, product quality (Factor 6) and efficient management (Factor 1) have occupied the second and third highest levels of importance, while supportive environment (Factor 4), capital accessibility (Factor 5), and marketing strategy (Factor 2) have been perceived as the fourth, fifth and sixth important factors respectively. However, since the means of these factors have dispersed within a short range (3.3814—4.4781), the differences between ranks are quite small. The following discussion focuses on each of these six factors and relates the results to those reported in the existing literature.

Customer orientation

As perceived by the CEOs who responded to our questionnaire survey, customer orientation is the most important factor for the success of their enterprises. This factor is characterised by four variables, namely, commitment to customer satisfaction, good relations with customers, good service and delivery system, and competitive prices of products.

Customer orientation, which is often synonymous with *market orientation*, has been defined in the literature as an enterprise culture or philosophy that characterises an organisation's disposition to deliver superior value to its customers continuously (Slater and Narver, 1994). Peter Drucker (1954), the well-known management expert, emphasised this customer-oriented

philosophy to American manufacturers almost half a century ago by stating that the sole purpose of a firm was “to create and keep customers”.

Product Quality

Product quality has been perceived as the next most important success factor. This factor is associated with three variables: availability of quality raw materials, use of new technology and automation, and maintaining high quality of products. In a highly competitive market environment, customers obviously look for high quality products at reasonably low cost (Chaganti and Chaganti, 1983). According to the findings of a survey conducted in Japan on a sample of successful small manufacturing enterprises, high quality of products has been perceived by their owner/managers as the second most important success factor (Wijewardena and Cooray, 1996).

Efficient Management

Another most highly rated success factor is efficient management. This finding is consistent with the universally accepted phenomenon that efficient management is crucial for the success of any type of organisation. Moreover, while a sizeable amount of studies have identified poor management as a major cause of business failures. Many studies have found that efficient management is the key to business success (Aquino, 1990; Bharadwaj and Menon, 1993; Steiner and Solem, 1988). Efficient management in our analysis consists of seven variables, namely, efficient team of management, production efficiency and productivity, strong and exemplary leadership, systematic planning for the future, acquiring high-calibre workforce, good relations with employees, and effective cost management.

Supportive Environment

This factor is made up of three major sources of support that are crucial for the success of Indian manufacturing enterprises. They are the open economic policy of the government, political stability and peaceful environment in the country, and government assistance/tax intensives. Our respondents have perceived this factor as the fourth most important contributor to the success of their enterprises.

The next important ingredient of the supportive environment includes various forms of government assistance such as tax incentives, infrastructure facilities and industrial zones, and loan facilities through state banks particularly for small and medium-scale industries. These different forms of government assistance undoubtedly contribute to the development of manufacturing enterprises in the country.

Capital Accessibility

Obviously, capital accessibility is an essential prerequisite for setting up and successfully operating a manufacturing business. Therefore, the lack of capital has been widely cited in the literature as a major constraint particularly for the development of small manufacturing enterprises throughout the world. In addition to the capital invested by owners in the form of equity or share capital, manufacturing enterprises often need both short and long-term funds in the form of loans and overdrafts to finance numerous capital projects and day-to-day operations. The Indian government has set up several financial institutions such as the Industrial Development Bank and the Development Finance Corporation for helping manufacturers in financing their long-term capital investment projects while many commercial banks also provide both short and long-terms loan facilities to businesses. As shown in Table 4, the respondents in SMEs of our sample have attached a greater degree of importance to this factor than their counterparts in large enterprises.

The importance of this factor for the success of manufacturing enterprises in India particularly evidenced by the fact that the impressive inflow of foreign direct investment (FDI) in response to the policy reforms initiated in 1977 has been a major contributor to the expansion of manufacturing industry in the country during the past two decades.

Marketing Strategy

The factor referred to as marketing strategy in our study encompasses four specific variables, namely, advertising and promotional activities, use of external advisory services, emphasis on specialised markets, and new product development. The use of external advisory services seems to be relevant to this factor because it is common among some manufacturers to use such services in designing and implementing their marketing strategies. Placing emphasis on specialised markets is believed to be particularly beneficial to firms engaged in export trade.

Similarly, it is realistic to see that the CEOs in our sample firms have attached a high degree of importance to new product development as a part of their marketing strategy because gathering information on customer reaction to the existing product in order to introduce quality improvements or to design a new product is necessary for overcoming the problems associated with product obsolescence and resultant declines in sales.

Conclusions

Through an empirical investigation, this study has identified six principal factors that are perceived to be major contributors to the success or growth of manufacturing firms in India. These factors in their order of importance are customer orientation, product quality, efficient management, supportive environment, capital accessibility, and marketing strategy.

Finally, it is important to note that there is a need to replicate this study by using more measures and a larger sample that covers manufacturing enterprises operating in different geographical areas of the country. A comparison of Indian firms with their counterparts in other developing countries would also be a fruitful future research avenue.

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